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2nd Instrument Release and Laboratory Testing Report

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Disclaimer

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RAMONES project's main objective is to close the current marine radioactivity under-sampling gap and foster new interdisciplinary research in ocean ecosystems. RAMONES will invest a significant effort to provide tools to enable long-term data acquisition missions, rapid deployments, low cost per information byte, and propose new AI and Robotics-driven and supported methodologies, being ambitious to eventually offer scaled-up solutions to researchers, policy makers and communities. All these may be achieved by combining state-of-the-art (SoA) methodologies and equipment from various disciplines in a well-balanced synergy, and designing new and effective methodologies targeting the marine environment, which will provide efficient response to existing natural and man-made hazards, and shape future policies for the global population. RAMONES will additionally contribute to shaping a blueprint on Environmental Intelligence in the EU and worldwide.

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List of acronyms

Acronym	Description
α SPECT	Underwater Alpha Spectrometer
CHERI	Cherenkov Imager
CTD	Conductivity, Temperature and Pressure Sensor
CZT	Cadmium Zinc Telluride
DCR	Dark Count Rate
FEPE	Full Energy Peak Efficiency
FWHM	Full Width at Half Maximum
GASPAR	Gamma Spectrometer for Marine Radioactivity Studies
HPGe	High-Purity Germanium
MCA	Multi-channel Analyzer
(N)UV	(Near) Ultraviolet
OEM	Original Equipment Manufacturer
SIMBLA	Simulation of Detectors and Benthic Laboratory
SoA	State of the Art
SPAD	Single Photon Avalanche Diode Arrays
SUGI	Submarine Gamma Imager

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Abstract

RAMONES develops a new fleet of instruments to perform continuous and in situ measurements of natural and artificial radioactivity in the marine environment as part of its main objectives. Functional prototypes of the instruments are being developed, optimized, and validated in the lab, considering specific functional characteristics, optimizing integrated solutions, and fine-tuning the overall architecture. The built prototypes will be further tested during the field experiments planned in the Milos Island.

Three types of RAMONES instruments, namely GASPARG, γ -Sniffers and SUGI, are built for the detection and monitoring of gamma radiation. The first two focus on detection and spectroscopy, while SUGI offers gamma radiation imaging capabilities, providing information for the direction of the detected events, via Compton imaging or other collimation solutions.

α SPECT implements a novel and innovative solution for the underwater detection of alpha particles, based on a radon progeny collector and a gas ingestion subsystem. CHERI on the other hand, aims to detect Cherenkov radiation in underwater environments via task-specific, highly sensitive camera systems.

Regarding the platforms on which the instruments will be integrated on, a benthic laboratory is developed with the ability to hosting any combination of the RAMONES instruments, while special mounting solutions are developed for mounting γ -Sniffers on underwater gliders for scanning the water column for gamma radiation. All RAMONES instruments can also be mounted on ROVs, offering easier relocation to regions of suspected activity.

This report describes the current state of development of the RAMONES instruments.

1 Introduction

1.1 Context

This report is deliverable D1.3 “*2nd Instrument Release and Laboratory Testing Report*” of the H2020 RAMONES project. The report is mainly a product of the work performed in all tasks of WP1 “*Design and Develop Novel Underwater Gamma Radiation Instruments*”.

1.2 Contents and Rationale

The main purpose of this document is to present the instruments being designed, developed and tested for all seafloor, water-column and sea surface radioactivity measurements and mapping operations. The document presents the developed instruments in their current functional form and discusses their overall integration into a common scheme, considering aspects pertaining to the platforms on which they will be mounted.

The document functions as the main reference regarding RAMONES instrumentation for every member of the consortium to extract details on the targeted specifications, operational characteristics and integration properties and standards, establishing a framework for the team to effectively carry out all the project activities which directly or indirectly depend on the instrument design and the specifications. Moreover, it drives innovation in instrumentation development and designs optimising for efficient deployment in an autonomous, synergetic scheme during the RAMONES lifetime.

The final version of the instruments will be presented on the last revision of this document, including their testing in the field experiments that are planned in Milos Island.

1.3 RAMONES Instrumentation and Development Status

Benthic Laboratory

A functional prototype of the control unit and the powering subsystem of the benthic laboratory have been developed and tested in the lab environment.

γ -Sniffers

γ -Sniffers are at a very mature state. The detector module has been chosen and procured (RITEC μ SPEC4000) and, based on this solution, their underwater housing design and manufacturing has been completed, passing all the stages from initial design, simulations, refinement, machining and final assembly. Dedicated software has been developed based on the ROS middleware for configuring and collecting data from the instrument. The γ -Sniffers have been calibrated and thoroughly tested in a lab environment, both in the air and in the water, and relevant minimum detection activities have been identified.

GASPAR

There is no activity to report yet due to late procurement, which at the time of submission of this deliverable is still pending.

SUGI

SUGI is in a development state. The detector subsystem, including a high voltage module, has been chosen and procured (IDEAS GDS-100). Regarding SUGI underwater housing, both a dedicated solution and one integrated with the benthic laboratory have been foreseen. A

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dedicated Python API has been developed based on the detector subsystem communication protocol for configuring the system and data logging.

αSPECT

The design of the instrument has progressed, with the radon progeny collector subsystem been finalized. The gas ingestion subsystem is being actively developed at this stage.

CHERI

Two complementary solutions for the sensing unit of the CHERI instrument are being developed. One is based on a high-resolution high-sensitivity UV camera, and the other on a single photon camera. The single photon camera (SPC3 from Micro Photon Devices) has been tested during the demo period in which the camera has been kindly provided by the manufacturer. The SPC3-based solution is currently halted due to delays in the sensor procurement. The UV camera has been procured and the first prototype of the UV based solution has been tested in a lab environment.

1.4 Structure of the document

Section 2 discusses simulations related to instrument development (SIMBLA); Section 3 presents the development status of the Benthic laboratory. Section 4 to 7 present the current status of each of the RAMONES instruments, namely, γ -Sniffers, SUGI, α SPECT and CHERI. Finally, Section 8 concludes the document.

2 SIMBLA - SIMulations of detectors and development of the Benthic Laboratory (Task 1.2)

Due to the harsh conditions prevailing at the marine environment, restrictions are arising regarding the geometries, the materials as well as the thicknesses of the materials that can be used for the detector's housing. For that reason, simulations with Geant4 code were carried out by changing the aforementioned parameters in order to find the most appropriate combination. Figure 1 illustrates the first housing geometry that was simulated which is like the one of a submarine. The CZT detector along with its housing was placed inside a cubic water tank of 27m³ filled with pure water (H₂O). The simulations were carried out with a point-like ¹⁵²Eu source placed at 10cm distance from the housing's entrance window by varying, firstly, the material of the housing. The materials studied were Plexiglass, 6082-T6 hard anodized aluminium type III and 6Al-4v grade 5 titanium with 2mm thickness each. All the simulations were performed for 10⁸ events. The electronic components and circuits were omitted due to limited information from the manufacturer. The Geant4 version that was used was the 4.10.

Figure 1: Simulated geometry of the detector and its housing for the initial simulations

As Figure 2 depicts, there is a difference of the simulated results depending on the material. More specifically, the simulated counts are 18% less for the Titanium housing compared to the Plexiglass. This difference is falling to 4% between the Aluminum and Plexiglass.

Figure 2: Simulated spectra for a point-like ^{152}Eu source placed at 10 cm distance from the housing's entrance window for three different materials

Thus, the most appropriate material for our needs is Aluminium or Plexiglass instead of Titanium since the signal losses are a lot less. Between Aluminium and Plexiglass, the type of Aluminium that was simulated provides corrosion protection which is the most common damage inside the aquatic environment and for that reason it is preferred more than the plexiglass. After the selection of the housing's material that fulfils our needs, simulations were continued by varying its geometry. Figure 3 illustrates the three geometries that were studied. The first one is a cylinder with a diameter of 4 cm and length of 10 cm with a dome in front of the detector's entrance window. The second one is a cylinder with a diameter of 6 cm and length of 10cm with flat ends. In this geometry, the detector's entrance window is facing the curved part of the cylinder. The third one is a 64 cm³ box.

Figure 3: Three different simulated geometries of the detector's housing

(a) Cylinder with dome

(b) Cylinder with flat end

(c) Box

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Figure 4: Simulated spectra for a point-like ^{152}Eu source placed at 10 cm distance from the housing's entrance window for three different geometries

In Figure 4, it can be noticed that the difference of the simulated spectra between the cylinder with the dome and the cylinder with the flat ends can be considered negligible ($\sim 2.7\%$). But this is not the case for the cubic geometry for which the differences with the other two reach 48%. For that reason, the geometries that can be used are the cylindrical ones. Since our aim is to submerge the spectrometers at high sea depths ($\sim 500\text{m}$ and more), from the mechanical point of view, the cylinder with the dome is more resistant at 50 tm. Additionally, it fits nicely inside the autonomous underwater gliders where the spectrometers will be placed. So, the cylinder with the dome (see Figure 3 (a)) will be used for the rest of the simulations. The next aspect that had to be investigated was the thickness of the selected material. Figure 5 shows the simulated results for three different thicknesses. It can be observed that the difference of the simulated counts can be considered negligible (less than 3%) so any of these three thicknesses can be used.

Figure 5: Simulated spectra for a point-like ^{152}Eu source placed at 10 cm distance from the housing's entrance window for three different thicknesses of 6082-T6 hard anodized aluminium type III

3 Benthic Laboratory

The stationary benthic laboratory platform will host the radioactivity detectors and imaging instruments at the sea bottom for long-term, high-resolution measurements. Moreover, it will serve as a data relay point and positioning aid for the autonomous underwater gliders (AUGs). The benthic laboratory will have the capability to include all the radioactivity instruments that will be developed in RAMONES (described in the following sections), as well as a standard conductivity, temperature, and pressure sensor (CTD), control unit, communications, and energy modules.

The development of the benthic laboratory platform has been started and advancements have been made in the control unit (hardware and software) including sensors connectivity and the energy subsystem. Moreover, the familiarization and integration of the communications and acoustic realizer systems has been initiated with the delivery of the modules from partner EVOLOGICS.

3.1 CONTROL UNIT

The control unit is the heart of the platform. It is based in a low power single board computer (SBC) and includes all the related electronic modules for instruments connectivity, communications control, data management and logging, power cycling scheduling and management to reduce overall energy consumption and increase platform autonomy.

A prototype control unit has been developed and has been tested already with the available RAMONES instruments (γ -Sniffer, SUGI, CHERI UV camera, and CTD) in the laboratory and it will be tested in the sea in the forthcoming Milos field experiments (**Error! Reference source not found.**).

Figure 6: Control unit prototype internals connected with γ -Sniffer

Hardware

A Raspberry Pi 4 with 8 Gb of RAM has been chosen for SBC because it balances good processing capabilities with low energy requirements and a large and reliable software community for support. It is combined with a Witty Pi 4 L3V7 that provides power management and scheduling capabilities, real-time clock, and battery backup.

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It supports a number of hardware protocols for connecting the instruments, including 10 ports of Gigabit Ethernet (GigE), USB (4 ports), 5 Serial ports (TTL with the option for RS232 level shifters), and the native GPIO pins from the SBC that some are used to remote switch the instruments via power MOSFETs.

There are two options for external GigE network connectivity; the first is with a short (2 m) underwater cable for connecting with an ROV or other compatible asset; the second is via fibre optic cable that allows long range and high-speed communications with shore stations. The last one is very useful for real-time viewing of measurements while testing at different depths either stand-alone or via ROV.

Software

The operating system of the SBC is Ubuntu 20.04 LTS and datalogging and control is based on the robotic operation system (ROS), version Noetic. ROS is a well-defined robotic framework that is also widely used in underwater robotic and sensory systems. All the robotic platforms and instruments of RAMONES are developed using ROS which provides a common data messaging and storing framework.

The current benthic laboratory software and γ -Sniffer drivers with their relevant instructions have been uploaded to the common RAMONES GitHub software repository. It is worth to note that the γ -Sniffer drivers that developed for the benthic lab are also ready to be used for the gliders.

3.2 ENERGY MODULES

The first prototypes of high energy battery systems have been developed and will be tested in the field in forthcoming Milos experiments.

Three power banks have been developed using rechargeable Li-ion batteries cells (Figure 7). Each power bank is in 4S12P configuration with a nominal capacity of 600 Wh. It is housed in a hard anodized 6061-T6 aluminium enclosure that is depth rated for 950 m. It features a 2 m power supply cable, charger balancing connector, fuse protection, electronic switch, and pressure relief valve.

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Figure 7: Underwater power banks

Two power electronics modules have been developed for safely controlling the high energy that is stored in these power banks. The first is an electronic switch, capable of switching up to 80 A of current. The second is a load distribution module where two or more battery banks are connected in parallel and the module provides power from the battery with the higher voltage until they balance and then is sharing power from all banks (Figure 8).

Figure 8: Electronic switch (left). Load distribution module (right)

Raw battery voltage is fed to the benthic laboratory where appropriate DC-DC converters distribute the proper power to each module / instrument. This allows the power banks to be agnostic to where and how the power is distributed simplifying development.

4 γ -Sniffers (Task 1.4)

Hardware

Two prototype pressure tolerant housings have been developed for performing initial testing of the μ SPEC4000 spectrometer with 4 cm³ CZT crystal (figure XX). They are constructed with hard anodized aluminium 6082-T6. The overall wall thickness is 2 mm and are pressure rated for 600 m depth.

The two prototypes are identical except the connection cable. One has a standard 10 m USB cable for facilitating lab and field testing with a laptop. The second has 2 m of underwater cable with special connectors for connecting it in the Benthic Lab or an ROV.

Figure 9: The complete γ -Sniffer instrument

Software

Communication with the instrument is performed either with its native MS Windows app or via a Linux driver developed inhouse by partner. The driver is based on the robotic operation system (ROS), version Noetic and the Ubuntu 20.04 LTS. ROS is a well-defined robotic framework that is also widely used in underwater robotic and sensory systems. All the robotic platforms and instruments of RAMONES are developed using ROS which provides a common data messaging and storing framework.

The driver is designed for publishing the measurements and settings in ROS topics for allowing communication with other control software in gliders or the benthic lab. The measurements are saved in two different formats. The first is the *.spe format for maximum compatibility with the one used by the native MS Windows software. The second is in rosbags format for compatibility with the ROS framework.

The driver has been programmed for allowing a number of settings variables to be changed before each measurement cycle and for easy addition of other settings variables if it became necessary after testing.

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The γ -Sniffer drivers with their relevant instructions have been uploaded to the common RAMONES GitHub software repository and are ready to be used for the gliders and the benthic Lab.

MDA measurements in air

Minimum detectable activity (MDA) is of major importance, regarding the evaluation of the measurement ability of the system and method. MDA is calculated using the following equation [1]:

$$MDA = \frac{k^2 + 2k\sqrt{B(1 + \frac{N}{2m})}}{FEPE \cdot I_\gamma \cdot LT}$$

where, k is the coefficient corresponding to the confidence level chosen for the MDA value, B is the background estimation under the photopeak studied, N is the number of channels contained in the photopeak region of interest and m is the number of channels to the left and to the right of the photopeak, considered for estimating the background continuum. Finally, FEPE is the full energy peak efficiency for the photopeak studied, I_γ its possibility of emission (relative intensity) and LT the live time of the measurement.

Initially, a GR1 CZT spectrometer (1 cm³ CZT crystal) was studied, by carrying out measurements in the air with a calibrated ¹³⁷Cs point source. Measurements each for 1800 seconds were performed, for various distances between the source and the front window of the detector. Results are presented in Figure 10, by implementing two different confidence levels on the expressed MDA value.

In addition, the measurement for $d=10$ cm was repeated by shielding the detector using 5 cm thick Pb bricks. Our goal was to examine the effect of the shielding on the overall background registered from the detector and consequently on the MDA value achieved. Three different setups were tested, including one without any shielding, an approximation of a 2π and a 4π shielding.

Table 1: Total count integrals and MDA values for the measurements with and without any shielding

Shielding setup	Total counts	MDA [95% Conf. level] (kBq)
No	82609±287	3.7
2 π	89585±299	3.3
4 π	95815±309	3.3

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Figure 10: MDA values for ¹³⁷Cs, measured in air with the GR1 spectrometer for various source to detector distances expressed for two different confidence levels

Figure 11: Comparing full energy spectra of a ¹³⁷Cs point source measured with and without shielding (left) and focused on the photopeak region (right)

The presence of the shielding seems to increase the total area of the ¹³⁷Cs photopeak as well as the Compton continuum. Additionally, the characteristic x-ray of Pb arises, while the backscatter peak decreases.

The MDA value slightly improves by enhancing the detector shielding. This is caused by the suppression of the background under the area of the photopeak analysed.

MDA measurements in water

A fertiliser known to have ⁴⁰K content was prepared as a source to estimate the MDA value for the certain radionuclide during an underwater measurement. The first step was to calculate the specific activity of ⁴⁰K contained in the fertiliser. To do so, a sample was weighed and encapsulated in a plastic cup. A reference IAEA-154 standard material [2], with known ⁴⁰K specific activity, was used for cross calibrating the fertiliser sample. Both materials had the same shape and volume to replicate self-absorption effects for the measurements. A fully-shielded HPGe detector was preferred for the measurement.

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Then, the fertiliser was diluted in water contained in a cylindrical plastic container in order to establish a homogeneous radioactive volume source. Measurements were performed not only with the GR1 spectrometer but also with a μ SPEC4000 spectrometer (4 cm³ CZT crystal). In both cases, the detector was encapsulated in a waterproof plastic housing. In Table 2, the overall specifications of the measurement setup are illustrated.

Figure 12: Picture (left) and representation (right) of the measurement setup

Table 2: Main parameters of the experiment for MDA calculations in water

Experiment parameter	Value
Fertiliser specific activity (kBq/kg)	10.27
Water volume (L)	38.79
Mass of diluted fertiliser (kg)	1.25
Total activity of the water source (kBq/L)	0.331

The MDA for the radioisotope ⁴⁰K was calculated for both detectors and was expressed for two different confidence levels. Results are summarised in the next table.

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Table 3: MDA values for ⁴⁰K calculated for both detectors and two different confidence levels

Detector	Live time (sec)	MDA [95% Conf. level] (Bq/L)	MDA [90% Conf. level] (Bq/L)
GR1	8×10 ⁴	56.1	43.3
μSPEC4000	7.2×10 ⁴	20.9	16.2

On the following graph, a comparison between the count rates registered from both detectors during the measurements described above is presented. Any differences are mainly due to the difference in the dimensions of the CZT crystal.

Figure 13: Comparison of the count rate from both detectors regarding the measurement of ⁴⁰K in water

5 SUGI - Submarine Gamma Imager (Task 1.5)

The Submarine Gamma Imager (SUGI) is a novel underwater γ -radiation imager. The goal of SUGI is to detect, localize and identify radioactivity in its surrounding area. The SUGI is designed to be mounted both on the benthic laboratory and ROV. When mounted on the benthic laboratory, SUGI can perform prolonged measurements from a static location, thus collecting better statistics regarding the surrounding radioactivity. On the other hand, mounting SUGI on an ROV gives the possibility of moving the instrument in the vicinity of regions of interest where significant radioactivity events are suspected. The multipurpose design of SUGI enhances its versatility making it suitable across diverse radioactivity monitoring and mapping scenarios.

After considering the available options for the detector and the supporting electronics, the GDS-100 from IDEAS has been selected and procured for building the SUGI instrument. GDS-100, being an integrated solution comprising detector modules, acquisition electronics and management PCB in an OEM product, offers an optimal trade-off between customization ability and product maturity. GDS-100 (Figure 14) supports up to four GDS-10 detector modules. Each detector module (Figure 15) is paired with a 11×11 pixelated CdZnTe (CZT) crystal and has 121+2 detection channels, 121 anode channels for the 11×11 array and 2 cathode channels. This configuration allows to perform Compton imaging by analysing the spatial and temporal correlation amid the events registered by the device, either within the same detector or across different ones. Compton imaging is based on the Compton scattering phenomenon (Figure 16), which under certain assumptions allows to estimate the direction of incident radiation. The analysis of multiple events allows to generate omnidirectional (spherical) images showing the direction of radioactivity sources surrounding the detector. Moreover, the detector, through appropriate calibration, reports the energy of the gamma rays that gave rise to the corresponding event, allowing to perform spectrometry of the incoming gamma radiation. The data collected from GDS-100 provide all the necessary information to perform the aforementioned analysis, i.e., Compton imaging and spectrometry.

Figure 14: GDS-100 system from IDEAS

Figure 15: GDS-10 detector module from IDEAS

Figure 16: Compton scattering (source: MIT OpenCourseWare)

The SUGI instrument, besides the GDS-100 system, comprises a High Voltage module, necessary for providing suitable bias voltage to the CZT detectors, a Raspberry Pi 4 single-board computer hosting all software necessary for logging, processing, and analysing all data collected from GDS-100, and auxiliary electronic and network components (i.e., power modules, relays, network switches, etc). All these components are contained in a custom-made underwater housing. A preliminary prototype of SUGI is shown in Figure 17. The housing thickness and material, as well as the placement of the components in the housing, have been chosen based on simulations performed in the context of SIMBLA (see Section 2), and is a balance between as-small-as-possible gamma radiation absorption and to guarantee a depth rating of at least 500 meters. Specifically, an aluminum alloy 6061-T6 of 4 mm thickness has been chosen with a hard anodized treatment for withstanding the expected pressure (50 bar) and the corrosiveness of sea water. The possibility of attaching different collimators (e.g., pinhole, multi-hole, etc) and the final instrument design will be decided based on laboratory and field tests, detector efficiency, scene coverage and the overall cost.

Figure 17: SUGI prototype under testing with the Benthic Lab

Data logging, processing, and communication with the GDS-100 is achieved using the TCP/IP protocol. TCP packets are used for system configuration and UDP packets for data readout. A versatile python API is under development, according to the GDS-100 TCP/UDP packet specifications (Doppio format), to allow real-time configuration, system health monitoring (e.g., key component voltage, temperatures, etc.), and data readout. A python implementation was favoured, to allow easy deployment both on x86-64 desktop/workstation systems for development purposes, and on AARCH64 embedded computers, as Raspberry Pi 4, for testing and final deployment. The adopted solution allows for both online real-time processing and for off-line batch processing. Processing will include simple tasks as reporting of total event counts and counts per second, the construction of the histogram reporting the energies of the recorded events, as well as more complex tasks as the construction of spherical heatmaps based on Compton imaging.

The detection and monitoring of possible sources is performed off-board via batch processing of the collected data, both due to the increased computational power required and to allow the on-board processing unit to focus mainly on the management of the whole platform. Simulations and extensive experimentation are carried out to study the computational and bandwidth requirements of the instrument, to offer suitable scheduling of the measurement pipeline.

Table 4 summarizes the main characteristics of SUGI.

Table 4: Design characteristics for SUGI

Name	SUGI
Placement	Benthic Lab - Remote operated vehicle

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Housing	Study different housing materials (Polymer, Aluminium, Titanium, Alloys)
Mounting	Multi-module array
Nominal Energy Range	50-30000 keV
Nominal resolution	FWHM ~2.5% for 662 keV
Crystal Operational Voltage	High voltage-low current (instrument integrated circuit)
Power consumption	<6W
Interfaces	Eth - TCP/IP
Computational demands	based on scheduling, reactive behaviours based on on-board processing, detailed analysis to be done off-board
Bandwidth	<20 Mbps (rate: <1K recorded events per second)

6 α SPECT - Underwater Alpha Spectrometer (Task 1.6)

6.1 Radon Progeny Collector

The design of the radon progeny collector has been finalised. Instead of solid walls, the detector will use metallic meshes in order to assist the intermediate pumping between measurements. An additional study was performed in order to optimise space for the electronic units. Towards this goal, the cylindrical 8" housing has been divided into 3 spaces: the first one is an opening of 140° , a dedicated space, sufficiently large for the electronics units (a custom unit with the preamps, analogue adder, Cockcroft–Walton generator, and the multichannel analyser). The other two 110° volumes will be used as precipitation chambers, for the radon progenies to be collected on the detectors. This geometry allows for the minimization of cable length between the detectors and the preamplifiers, thus minimization of noise. The supporting structure for the detectors, the high voltage mesh, and the electronics will be designed to consist of assemblable 3d-printed components.

Figure 18: Final design for the compartmentalization of the underwater 8" housing

Test prints have been initialised in order to optimize the matching between the PDB-V612-2 detectors and the printed components. In Figure 19, a shorter, test version of the silicon detector base is shown. The size, shape and depth of the pocket is optimised to hold the detectors, with minimum obstruction to the electric field.

Figure 19: Test print of the customised silicon detector base

6.2 Gas separation and conditional module

A system for extracting radon gas from high pressure water has been designed and currently is under components procurement for building an initial prototype. The design concept is illustrated with block diagrams in Figure 20.

Figure 20: Gas separation and conditional module block diagram

A water pump (either from CTD or standalone) circulates the water at the wet part of the gas separation membrane. The membrane attachment is based on a patent from a partner collaborator and is designed to support the membrane from the high pressures (50 bar) of the operational area. Gas separation is happening naturally due to the low pressure inside the module. A low power fan circulates the extracted gases in the chamber via a series of filters for removing humidity and CO₂ that is expected to be in very high concentrations in the hydrothermal field.

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A CO₂, pressure, and temperature monitoring system ensures that the pressure in the analyser chamber will be always in the desired specifications by controlling the vacuum pumps and the purge valves. It is also logging all the data from the sensors and control actions for post processing.

The system is designed to have two modes of measurement operations. The first is to behave as a free flow system by continuously controlling the valves and the vacuum pump. This mode follows the concept of terrestrial commercial instruments; however it has a higher power consumption. In the second mode, the extracted gas is feeling the analysing chamber up to specific pressure and then the isolation valve closes, leaving a fixed volume of gas for measurement. After the measurement cycle is finished, the gas is purged into a storage tank using the vacuum pump. The storage tank has a relief valve for equalizing its pressure with the environment. This will also ensure that no high pressure exists in the system when it is recovered on the surface.

7 CHERI - Cherenkov Imager (Task 1.7)

The Cherenkov Imager (CHERI) is a novel imager for detecting Cherenkov radiation in underwater environments. Due to the low intensity of the Cherenkov radiation in most underwater scenarios, CHERI needs to have an extremely high sensitivity in the blue-violet-NUV (Near UV) spectrum, where Cherenkov has the highest intensity. Two complementary solutions have been promoted for the sensors based on which the instrument will be developed. The first is the SPC3 single photon camera from Micro Photon Devices with high photon detection efficiency and very low dark count rate. The second is a high-resolution, high-efficiency UV camera from PhotonFocus (MV4-D1280U-L01-GT). The two sensors are shown in Figure 21. The development of SUGI is based on both sensors due to their complementary nature, as one has low resolution and high pitch but can provide very accurate photon-level counts, while the other is based on a high-resolution CMOS sensor, showing high sensitivity and low-noise on the NUV spectrum.

Figure 21: SPC3 single photon camera from MPD (Left) and MV4 UV camera from PhotonFocus (right)

Regarding the SPC3 camera, its sensor is composed of 32x64 single-photon avalanche diodes (SPADs) with a pixel pitch of 150 μm . Compared to other single photon cameras, the SPC3 has a significantly higher photon efficiency in the violet and Near UV range, which is crucial for Cherenkov radiation detection. The SPC3 camera has been paired with a lens with very high transmittance (>90%) in the near-UV range. This setup has been calibrated both with respect to the detection sensitivity of each pixel, as well as the dark-counting rate (DCR) in terms of the sensor temperature. The SPC3 single photon camera has been kindly provided by Micro Photon Devices for a 30-days evaluation period. In this period multiple tests have been conducted for assessing the sensitivity of the device in the NUV spectrum with respect to low photon fluxes both in the air and in the water, as well as the dark count rate (DCR) of the device and their dependence with the sensor temperature. A detailed report of these experiments is included in D4.1. The procurement of the SPC3 has not been completed at this point.

The UV camera has been procured although the procurement was affected by a long lead time due to the worldwide shortage on electronics components reported by the manufacturer. Initial testing has been performed to assess the correct operation of the device. An underwater housing has been designed and developed, paying attention to the characteristics of the UV camera interface that is based on 10Gigbit Ethernet technology, thus requiring suitable network components.

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Appropriate lenses with a high (>80%) transmittance in the NUV spectrum have been acquired for both sensors. Due to the characteristics of the sensors, a wide-angle lens is used for the SPC3 camera, and a normal lens is used for the MV4 UV camera. This difference in the field-of-view of the two sensors further contributes to their complementarity in CHERI.

Figure 22: The housing hosting the hardware components and the MV4 UV camera.

When mounted on the benthic laboratory, it is critical to change the directionality of the CHERI instrument due to the relatively low directionality of the phenomenon and the limited field of view of the sensors. For this reason, it is considered that they are more suitable to be installed on an ROV for pointing the instrument to different directions. In any case, the instruments are designed to be ready to be installed on either platform. The characteristics of the CHERI instrument, based on both sensors (SPC3 and MV4 UV camera) are provided in Table 5.

Table 5: The basic features of CHERI

Name	CHERI
Placement	Benthic Lab – Remote operated vehicle
Housing	study different housing materials
Mounting	Fixed or pan-tilt mechanism
Single photon camera	
Resolution	32 x 64
Pixel pitch	150 um
Photon detection efficiency	up to 50% @ 400nm, improved NUV response

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Dark count rate	<90% of pixels with DCR < 100 c/s, < 95% of pixels with DCR < 1000 c/s
Power consumption	<5W
Interfaces	USB / Binary files
Computational demands	not-significant
Bandwidth	<4KB/frame
Associated modules	optical filter (sensitivity in blue spectrum)
CMOS UV camera	
Optical format	1"
Optical diagonal	12.13mm
Resolution	1280 x 1024
Pixel pitch	7.4 um
Dark current	200 e-/s @ 25°C
Spectral range	150 to 1000nm (to 10% of peak responsivity)
Responsivity	2500 x 10 ³ DN / (J/m ²) @ 580nm / 8bit
Quantum Efficiency	>85% @ 550nm, >30% @ 200-400nm
Dynamic range	53dB
Power consumption	< 13 W
Interfaces	10GigE
Associated modules	optical filter (sensitivity in blue spectrum)

8 Conclusions – Next stage of development

γ -Sniffers and SUGI are at a mature state of development and they have already been verified and tested in lab environment. The development of GASPAR on the other hand suffers from significant delays in the procurement of the main detection module.

The design of aSPECT is at an advanced state. Its development and manufacturing are expected to be completed in the following months, and lab tests will follow. Regarding CHERI, as the procurement of the Single Photon Camera also faces significant delays, an alternative solution based on a highly sensitive UV camera has been put forward. A prototype of the benthic lab is ready and has been tested in the lab environment.

Regarding the next stage of development, all the functional prototypes will be tested in the field experiments that will be carried out at Milos Island. The analysis of the data collected during the field experiments will offer invaluable information for the validation of the RAMONES instruments as well as possible adaptations that will be addressed in the final version of the instruments.

References

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